

IMPROVEMENTS IN A LONG-TERM PRESERVATION SYSTEM IN A COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT:

Social Science Data Archives (ADP) and National and University Library (NUK)

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CONTROL OVER VERSIONS / AUTOMATIC DATA HARVESTING

EVALUATION STUDY IN 2011

CHANGE NECESSARY

- 🤖 Metadata standards
- 😞 Local file system for storing + weekly backups.
- 😞 No **user** and **version** control.
- 😞 Using **several applications**.
- 😞 Need to **automate capture** of materials (SIP).
- 😞 Need to use **permanent identifiers**.

- Good practice in partners institutions (UKDA, ICSPR).
- Up to date technology support / new application should be **tailor maid** – to address current challenges / issues/ gaps.

Compliance with TRAC, Data Seal of Approval, and other archival standards.

Dublin Core	
Title	
Creator	
Subject	
Description	
Publisher	
Contributor	
Date (of file/material)	
Type	
Format (type, size, no. of pages, case Q, var Q)	
Identifier (Fedora, URN, COBISS, ISBN, ISSN)	
Source	
Language	
Relation (derived from, resolved in)	
Coverage (year, geographic)	
Rights	
Additional	
Original	
Date of entry	
Producer of material	
Material stored on	
Part of material (DDI)	
OAIS	
Production place	
Depositor of material	
Notes	
Diary of change	
Original name	

URN (UNIFORM RESOURCE NAME)

Can be developed and used **FREE OF CHARGE**.

Developed in collaboration with Slovene National and University Library.

URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:_____

URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SURVEYID TYPE VERSION_REVISION

Type of materials	Suggested appendix	Example
Related materials	_RM1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_RM1_V1_R1
Related publications	_RP1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_RP1_V1_R1
Other material	_OM1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_OM1_V1_R1
Data file	_D1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_D1_V1_R1
Questionnaire	_Q1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_Q1_V1_R1
Code list	_CL1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_CL1_V1_R1
Syntax	_SY1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_SY_V1_R1
Licence agreement	_LA1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_LA_V1_R1

Using two major system functions: the **URN generator** – service defining unique URN record for every object and the **URN resolver** – interpreter that connects a given URN record with a digital object.

PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER

PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER – STABLE REFERENCE

Digital publications have globally unique identifiers, with which they can be more reliably cited.

HTTP://WWW.DLIB.SI/?URN ← *replace with real URN*